

ELECTROMECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF HYDROXYAPATITE / BaTiO₃ COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Results on manufacturing and electromechanical properties of hydroxyapatite / BaTiO₃ ceramic composites with ceramic volume fractions $m \geq 0.7$ are reported. Experimental volume-fraction dependences of the piezoelectric coefficients $d_{31}^*(m)$, $d_{33}^*(m)$ and dielectric permittivity $\varepsilon_{33}^{*\sigma}(m)$ are explained using a composite model in terms of 1–3 and 2–2 connectivity.

Keywords: piezoelectric coefficient, dielectric permittivity, piezo-composite

EXPERIMENTAL

Recently, a variety of attempts have been made to create piezo-composites that combine the bio-active properties of hydroxyapatite (HA) with the electromechanical properties of lead-free ferroelectric ceramics (FC), such as barium titanate (BT) BaTiO₃ [1, 2]. Some possibilities of increasing piezoelectric activity and sensitivity for the HA / BT composite and the variations of its dielectric properties were previously discussed in papers [2, 3]. The aim of the present work is to report results concerning the manufacturing of the HA / BT composite, to show possibilities of modeling of the effective electromechanical properties and to discuss their features at high volume fractions of FC.

The HA / BT composite samples to be studied were manufactured via pressureless sintering with BT contents varying from 0 % to 100 % by volume. After ball milling the powders in zirconia media the powder compacts were uniaxially cold pressed at a pressure of 100 MPa. The diameter of the compacts was 15 mm with a thickness of typically 2 mm. The composites were sintered in air at 1300 °C for 2 h with a heating and cooling ramp rate of 60 °C / h. After sintering, the composites were ground flat and conducting silver ink electrodes were applied (RS Products 101–5621). Composites were corona poled, whereby a high potential difference was applied across the sample by a high-tension point source. Poling was carried out at 130 °C using a potential of 28 kV and a point source height of 70 mm. At room temperature, the piezoelectric coefficient d_{33}^* was measured using a Take Control PM25 piezometer at 97 Hz, the dielectric permittivity $\varepsilon_{33}^{*\sigma}$ of a stress-free sample was measured at 1 kHz using a

Solatron 1260 impedance analyzer and a 1296 dielectric interface using a voltage of 1 V_{rms}.

MODELLING OF EFFECTIVE ELECTROMECHANICAL PROPERTIES

A model of a porous piezo-active material based on the Pb(Zr, Ti)O₃-type FC has been applied [4] to describe the effective piezoelectric and dielectric properties of composites in a wide range of porosity level. Elements of the first type within the microstructure with 1–3 connectivity (i.e. piezo-active rods in a matrix) are predominately responsible for the piezoelectric effect of the composite along the poling axis OX_3 . Due to the presence of a second type of element with the microstructure with 2–2 connectivity (i.e. piezo-active layers) it is possible to vary anisotropy of the piezoelectric coefficients d_{3j}^* and dielectric permittivity $\varepsilon_{33}^{*\sigma}$ of the composite in a wide range. According to the model from work [4], the layer of the first type represents a matrix reinforced by cylindrical rods of ferroelectric ceramic which are lengthy and parallel to the OX_3 axis. The layer of the second type is a ferroelectric ceramic. Both the layers types are assumed to be randomly alternating in the OX_3 direction and lengthy in the OX_1 and OX_2 directions.

Modelling of the electromechanical properties of the HA / BT composite was undertaken to compare with our current experimental results. In our model, the layer of the first type comprises the BT ceramic rods (volume fraction m_r) surrounded by the HA matrix (volume fraction $1 - m_r$), and the volume fraction of the layers in the composite equals m_s (Fig. 1, a). The layer of the second type consists purely of ferroelectric BT ceramic and is characterised by the volume fraction $1 - m_s$ in the composite sample as a whole. Thus, the volume fraction of the piezo-active BT ceramic in this composite is given by

$$m_{FC} = m_s m_r + 1 - m_s \quad (1)$$

Averaging the properties of the components is performed in terms of the parameters m_r and m_s from Eq. (1). Averaging on m_r for the layer of the first type is carried out on the basis of formulae for 1–3 connectivity [5]. The evaluated electromechanical constants of this layer and the constants of the layer of the second type are further averaged on m_s in accordance with formulae [6] for 2–2 connectivity. It is assumed that the BT ceramic rods are in the form of elongated circular cylinders that are characterised by an aspect ratio (height to diameter) $\alpha_r \geq 5$. At this condition it is possible to avoid a distinct difference (over 10%) between the electromechanical constants of the 1–3 composite with infinite rods [5] and the electromechanical constants of a similar composite with finite rods [7]. In addition to the presence of BT and HA, the porosity m_p of the ceramic can be taken into account in an averaging procedure based on a self-consistent scheme [8]. This modelling scheme is able to predict the full set of the electromechanical constants of a piezo-active medium containing randomly distributed spherical air inclusions. In this case the averaging procedure on m_p is implemented on assumption that a size of each air inclusion is relatively small in comparison to the diameter of the BT ceramic rods in the layer of the first type.

In undertaking the averaging procedures, room-temperature elastic moduli and dielectric permittivity of HA are taken from work [9]. As far as the BT FC is

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of the HA / BT composite (a) with a high volume fraction of FC $m = m_s m_r + 1 - m_s$ and experimental (triangles) and calculated (curves) effective piezoelectric coefficients d_{3j}^* (b, c, in pC / N) and dielectric permittivity $\varepsilon_{33}^{*\sigma}$ (d, e) of the HA / BT composites. Graph (e) was built for a case of the porous FC component (volume fraction of pores therein is $m_p = 0.05$). Curves 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 in graphs b–e relate to a volume fraction of the BT rods in the first-type layers $m_r = 0.01, 0.05, 0.10, 0.20, \text{ and } 0.30$, respectively.

concerned, the literature contains two full sets of the electromechanical constants [10, 11] measured on poled FC samples at room temperature. However, neither the dielectric permittivity $\varepsilon_{33}^{(BT),\sigma}$ nor piezoelectric coefficients $d_{3j}^{(BT)}$ of the pure BT FC [10, 11] correspond exactly to the constants measured in this work (see triangles at $m_{FC} = 1$ in Figs. 1, b–d) or previously [2]. To avoid this discrepancy in the initial stage of averaging, alternative sets of the electromechanical constants of the BT ceramic have been calculated by taking into account a mobility of 90° domain walls in grains. According to results [12], the electromechanical constants of the BT ceramic depend on a parameter $\gamma = (Hc)^{-1} \cdot 10^6$ Pa where H is an average width of the 90° domain and c is a parameter involved in an equilibrium equation $cx = f$. In this equation x is a domain-wall displacement and f is a thermodynamic pressure that acts on the domain wall under weak external fields [12]. Examination of the experimental data for the pure BT FC ($m_{FC} = 1$) suggests that the $d_{3j}^{(BT)}$ and $\varepsilon_{33}^{(BT),\sigma}$ values of the BT FC incorporated in the studied composites agree with the similar constants calculated using the self-consistent method for $\lg\gamma = -1.5$, i.e. the mobility of the 90° domain walls is relatively low.

COMPARISON OF MODELLING AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The $d_{3j}^*(m_{FC})$ and $\varepsilon_{33}^{*\sigma}(m_{FC})$ curves calculated for the HA / BT composites at fixed fraction m_r values are shown in Figs. 1, b–d. When taking into account porosity of the BT FC, a reduction in the dielectric response is attained at insignificant changes in the piezoelectric coefficients d_{3j}^* . For example, differences between the effective d_{3j}^* values calculated for $m_p = 0$ (Figs. 1, b and c) and $m_p = 0.05$ do not exceed 3% whereas a decrease in the $\varepsilon_{33}^{*\sigma}$ value becomes obvious (compare curves 1 to 5 in Figs. 1, d and e).

A considerable decrease in the d_{33}^* value is observed when decreasing the fraction of BT, m_{FC} (Fig. 1, c). The rapid decrease is accounted for by small differences between the elastic moduli of the BT and HA components. The HA/BT composite is different to many other piezo-composite structures such as porous piezo-ceramics or porous polymer / piezo-ceramic composites [4, 13] wherein the condition $d_{33}^*(m_{FC}) \approx \text{constant}$ is satisfied within a wide range. For the composite system studied here, the presence of the relatively high stiffness matrix (HA) in the layer of the first type (BT / HA) is a significant factor minimising the piezoelectric activity in the OX_3 direction. As m_r and m_{FC} from Eq. (1) increase, the effective piezoelectric coefficient $d_{33}^{(1)}$ of this layer increases at a slower rate than $d_{33}^{(1)}$ of a similar layer geometry with a polymer or porous matrix. The role of the stiff matrix in the layer of the first type is also observed by considering the piezoelectric anisotropy d_{33}^* / d_{31}^* of the HA / BT composite (compare data from Figs. 1, b and 1, c). At volume fractions $0.8 < m_{FC} < 1$ the d_{33}^* / d_{31}^* value changes only slightly, in comparison to the d_{33}^* / d_{31}^* of porous or other composite materials [4, 13].

The high stiffness of the HA matrix in the first layer (see Fig. 1, a) can be also regarded as a limiting factor in the poling process when a strain in the clamped BT ceramic grains would not develop and 90° domain reorientations would be impeded. As a consequence, a mechanical depolarisation of the composite and $d_{ij}^* \rightarrow 0$ [14] is

observed at moderate volume fractions of HA (about 0.3 as shown in Figs. 1, b and c). Finally, it follows from Figs. 1, b–e that a decrease in m_{FC} from 1 to 0.8 results in simultaneous shifting the experimental points of d_{3j}^* and $\varepsilon_{33}^{*\sigma}$ from curve 5 to curve 1: this shifting corresponds to evident decreasing the volume fraction m_r of the BT ceramic rods in the layer of the first type. Undoubtedly, such decreasing weakens piezoelectric activity of the studied composite along the poling axis OX_3 without serious prejudice to the dielectric response.

Volume fraction dependences of both the piezoelectric and dielectric properties at low porosity in the BT FC are shown in Table 1. Again the correlation between the calculated (see Table 1) and experimental (see triangles in Figs. 1, b–d) values of the three effective parameters is observed if to pass from $m_r = 0.30$ to $m_r = 0.01$ on decreasing the volume fraction of FC m_{FC} . This decreasing is closely associated with electromechanical decoupling that takes place in the composite sample along the OX_3 axis due to an “intervention” of HA into the BT FC medium.

CONCLUSIONS

Our present results on the experimental study and modelling of the effective electromechanical properties are concluded as follows.

(i) Samples of the piezo-active HA / BT composite have been manufactured, and their effective electromechanical properties have been studied in the FC volume fraction range of $0.7 \leq m_{FC} < 1$.

(ii) The model of the composite with elements of connectivity 1–3 and 2–2 (Fig. 1, a) has been put forward to interpret the volume fraction dependences of the effective electromechanical properties, e.g., d_{3j}^* and $\varepsilon_{33}^{*\sigma}$, in terms of two parameters, m_r and m_s (see Eq. (1), Fig. 1 and Table 1). The important role of the layers with 1–3 connectivity in forming the piezoelectric response of the studied HA / BT composite is shown.

(iii) Appropriate electromechanical constants of the BT ceramic are related to the range [12] wherein the low mobility of the 90° domain walls in the ceramic grains takes place. This circumstance can impede poling the studied composite in the presence of the stiff component (HA) that leads to loss of the piezoelectric activity of the composite at moderate volume fractions of HA.

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Table 1. Effective electromechanical constants calculated for the HA / BT composite with the porous ($m_p = 0.10$) ceramic component.^a

m_r	m_{FC}	d_{31}^* , pC / N	d_{33}^* , pC / N	$\epsilon_{33}^{*\sigma} / \epsilon_0$
0.30	0.70	-21.4	49.7	589
	0.75	-23.5	54.2	645
	0.80	-26.0	59.5	712
	0.85	-29.1	66.1	795
	0.90	-33.1	74.5	900
	0.95	-38.2	85.4	1040
0.20	0.70	-17.1	39.7	474
	0.75	-19.1	44.1	528
	0.80	-21.7	49.5	595
	0.85	-25.0	56.6	683
	0.90	-29.4	66.1	800
	0.95	-35.6	79.6	967
0.10	0.70	-10.9	25.3	307
	0.75	-12.6	28.9	351
	0.80	-14.8	33.7	410
	0.85	-17.9	40.3	491
	0.90	-22.4	50.4	614
	0.95	-30.0	67.0	817
0.05	0.70	-6.73	15.4	193
	0.75	-7.90	18.0	225
	0.80	-9.56	21.6	269
	0.85	-12.0	26.9	333
	0.90	-16.0	35.8	441
	0.95	-23.7	52.8	647
0.01	0.70	-2.49	5.47	78.8
	0.75	-3.04	6.69	93.6
	0.80	-3.83	8.43	115
	0.85	-5.09	11.2	148
	0.90	-7.39	16.3	209
	0.95	-12.9	28.6	358

^a At relatively low mobility of the 90° domain walls in grains of FC ($\lg\gamma = -1.5$ in terms of work [12]).

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